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Title:

Effect of dielectric barrier discharge (DBD) electrode configuration in the internal energy distribution of generated ions

Introduction: (120 words)

Dielectric barrier discharges are one of the most common plasma-based ion sources in mass spectrometry. The versatility in design and the ability to miniaturize the ion sources in addition to the observed performance have made them popular. Low-temperature plasma (LTP), dielectric barrier discharge ionization (DBDI), or flexible microtube plasma (F μ TP) are three examples of high-frequency alternative current operated plasmas. The different designs should involve different energies to the ions during the gas-phase ionization. As shown in the literature, Thermometer ions are the favorite molecules to study the internal energy deposited on the ions during positive ion mode ionization. Here, we proposed the investigation of different DBDI ion sources designs internal energy distributions evaluation.

Methods: (120 words)

Low-temperature plasma (LTP), dielectric barrier discharge ionization (DBDI), flexible microtube plasma (F μ TP), and corona discharge were evaluated. Benzylammonium thermometer ions 4-substituted with OCH₃, CH₃, H, F, and CF₃ were used to study the internal energy distributions of the different atmospheric pressure chemical ionization sources. The analyses were done in a Thermo Finnigan LTQ ion trap (Thermo Scientific). The analysis conditions were optimized to promote minimum thermometer ion dissociation caused by the ion transmission easing the determination of the internal energy supplied by the ion source.

Preliminary data: (300 words)

Plasma-based ion sources based on dielectric barrier discharges (DBDs) have been an important niche of study in ambient mass spectrometry. The ability to desorb the sample along with soft ionization displayed a powerful tool in analytical chemistry, especially for low polar molecules. Among the several plasma-based ion sources, dielectric barrier discharges stand out on design and construction versatility. Three main elements are necessary for DBD building: the alternating current power supply, the electrodes, and the dielectric material. The exchange of these elements enabled various configurations with different electrical behavior and unique gas-phase chemistry. The geometries could be simplified from the pin-to-ring in low-temperature plasma (LTP) to the two-ring dielectric barrier discharge ionization (DBDI) or the novel flexible microtube plasma (F μ TP).

Fundamental studies have shown how the variability of the configuration affects the actual reactant ions detected, and therefore gas-phase chemistry, sensitivity, desorption capabilities, or chemical coverage. The instrument used for the detection, the ion source position, or other external factors could lead to unfair comparisons. On the other hand, the bond dissociation energy of the so-called thermometer ions, and the associated internal energy deposition upon ion formation, could help to avoid any bias during ion sources comparison. The estimation of the energy supplied to the ions will help to boost the knowledge about the different DBD ion sources, facilitating the choice of the ion source based on the application, especially for labile compounds. In the present work, we evaluate the internal energy distributions of three different DBD sources: LTP, DBDI, and the F μ TP, and also compare them against the commercial APCI source based on corona discharge.

Novel aspect: (20 words)

Different DBDI ion source configurations were compared and evaluated in terms of internal energy supplied to the ions.